

Research Can Be Confusing: When do I ask questions?

In agreeing to start a research project, my goal is to begin training you as a scientist. We will ask questions that may not have clear answers. We will perform experiments that may not work. In science, things are not always straightforward. However, one of my goals is to equip you with skills to confront confusing aspects of science and find an answer. This research relationship thus requires that you ask questions, and ask them often! A quick guide on when to ask questions:

- 1) We are starting a new experiment
- 2) I am explaining code, software, anything mathematical
- 3) We are in the field and you want to poke a bug, but don't know if you should
- 4) You're confused
- 5) I said something
- 6) You've started a task that I've given you, worked on it a bit, but are more confused than ever*

*Independence is a *learned* skill. I do not expect you to work independently right away. Even if you completely understand a research task, I would rather you ask a question than sit staring at a computer for hours and hours. I DO expect questions and I expect you to try a task first. However, if you've been trying for 15-20 min and you haven't figured something out -- let's talk!

Communication - Early and Often

I break for tea often with students to chat about school, work, research, life, and more. You are welcome to come and have tea. If I am busy, I will reschedule with you. My policy is early and often! I want to help you achieve your research goals and learn new things on the way. If you are ever struggling, and we need to readjust expectations, know that you can come and chat.

How to address Dr. Salcedo or Dr. Mary

While working together, I prefer to be addressed as Dr. Salcedo (SAL-say-DOE) or Dr. Mary (MARE-ee). Colleagues and other professors may address me differently, but as we work together, please refer to me as specified.

How do you prefer to be addressed?

Please spell out your first/last name phonetically

Pronouns and Identity

My pronouns are she/her. If you choose to disclose your pronouns, please list below. If not, I will do my best to just use gender neutral language. Please note that lab members may use specific pronouns and if they make it clear or correct you, to please adjust to their preference.

_____ (Some pronoun examples: they/them, she/her, he/him)

Weekly Updates

In a research relationship with undergraduates I require a weekly update, sent on Fridays via email. If your research task is repetitive, we can discuss creative ways to make the weekly update more interesting (such as toggling between 1 and 2). Updates can take the form of:

- 1) An email with a paragraph (5-7 sentences) detailing what you've done for the week, what you've noticed, any questions, and how you're feeling about the project so far*
- 2) 1-2 slides (created in Keynote, Powerpoint, or Google slides) that have pictures, clear text and convey what you've been working on*

*You're welcome to write and create more than specified.

Reading Scientific Papers

An important part of the science process is figuring out if your questions and research interests are unique. We often search this out by using Google Scholar as a search engine with key words like, "insects" "flight" "biomechanics." In the beginning we will go over how to read a scientific paper, and I will ask you somewhat frequently to read a paper and tell me what you learned. (See also Tips and Tricks)

How long does it take to read a paper?

If you are trying to understand EVERYTHING a scientist did, it can be anywhere from 1-3 hrs of detailed reading. However, not every paper requires that -- or is fully worth your time. **I will specify how** I want you read a paper and often I will ask you to use a "skimming" process where I want you to briefly read a paper (15-25 min) by first:

- 1) Read the abstract—what's the main takeaway?
- 2) What animals are the authors focusing on and why?
- 3) Can you identify their major questions in the first few paragraphs of the paper?
- 4) Skip to the end, read the Discussion—do they give a more detailed takeaway?
- 5) Go back and look at each figure, reading captions
- 6) Ask yourself: Why did Dr. Salcedo give me this paper? How is it applicable to my current research task?
- 7) Write 3-5 sentences or bullet points with what you learned and why you it's useful for your research task*

*By the end of our research relationship, I hope that you will figure out how you best read papers and what "detailed" versus "skimming" means to you as a scientist. It's different for different people!

What if I don't understand a paper?

One, it might be outside your current breadth of knowledge, but also, it could be poorly written. I will assign papers that may be tough to get through, but have some knowledge nuggets or really

awesome figures. Don't assume you can't understand. Sometimes scientists write terrible papers...and they do get published.

Keeping a Lab Notebook

Transfer of knowledge is critical in keeping a happy and healthy lab. I expect you to keep a detailed lab notebook, which I will give you when you start a research project. These notebooks stay with the lab and ensure that the next person working on a project will know what you did. We will also take pictures as necessary to record any experimental designs. This will also help you keep track of what you did for your weekly update. I will ask for the lab notebook at the end of your research experience. You are welcome to take photocopies for future reference.

What should a general notebook entry include?

- 1) Date
- 2) Task for that day
- 3) Notes or observations about that task
- 4) Drawings of experiment techniques
- 5) Drawings of things you noticed (for example, you were working with beetles under a microscope and noticed how their feet are structured)
- 6) What you completed during the day*

*Note: sometimes research tasks are repetitive and involve lots of clicking a dot on a screen. I do expect lab entries every day you are present in the lab. There do not have to be drawings every day, but I expect points 1-3 and 6 for each entry.

Student Email Policy

I expect timely responses to emails. That is the primary way I communicate with my students when not in person. If I send you an email, please respond within 1-3 days, during business hours (anytime 8 am - 6 pm). If I am trying to coordinate experiments or scheduling, please try to respond within a day.

Dr. Salcedo's Email Style

Occasionally I may send you an email on the weekends or outside of business hours (8 am - 6 pm). However, I **do not** expect you to drop what you're doing and answer. I will do my best to only email you during business hours and I only expect responses during that time. Personally, I will do my best to respond to you within 1-2 days. I am often much faster (within the hour), but sometimes work requires some leeway.

What if I've emailed Dr. Salcedo and she has not responded?

While I would love to respond to every email in a timely way, sometimes work and numerous other emails clog my inbox. I'm only human! If you need a response quickly, please re-send your emails, daily if necessary. **If you're ever worried about bothering me—you're not.** If a topic is urgent, please use URGENT (in all caps) in the email subject line, followed by the topic

(example: URGENT: letter of rec due Dec 1st!). Urgent topics could include: Paper deadlines, letters of recommendation deadlines, personal emergencies, experimental needs (example: our grasshopper colony is out of lettuce). By marking “urgent” it means you need a response VERY soon (within a day or less). It also brings it to my attention more.

Letters of Recommendation

In a research relationship, communication is key. To write a strong letter of recommendation for your future endeavors (study abroad, interesting research programs, grad school), first, doing the research is key and is how I can write about you as a researcher. How have you grown as a researcher in our time together? What’s your thinking process? Note, a strong letter of recommendation does not hinge on whether or not your research “succeeds.” Research projects will often go awry, especially in short time frames, such as a semester or a summer. My letter will take note of how you dealt with those situations, and hopefully you asked questions, sought help or collaboration, or tried to create/design something new.

In requesting a letter of recommendation, please think: “early.” The earlier I know, the better. If a deadline is 1 month away, send me a reminder at 2 weeks. I will do my best to immediately input deadlines into my calendar. When requesting a letter: also fill out [my Google Form](#) and send me your resume/CV.

A last minute example: If there is a specific grant, fellowship, or other program that was put on your radar last minute (example: travel fellowship due in a week), that is okay, not ideal, but we should try! So, mark an email with “URGENT”, fill out the google form and send me the required documents.

Schoolwork

You are here to be a student, first and foremost. If research duties are ever interfering with schoolwork, please let me know and we will readjust. Occasionally we attend conferences, have publication deadlines, or collecting data in the field and may need your help. During those situations, it’s important to have the agreed-on help and not back out last minute. However, if there is a quick change, for example during a field experiment, always come to me to discuss.

Mental Health

To be a productive scientist, it’s important to monitor your own mental health and make sure, above all, you are respecting yourself. Therapy appointments are common (I have my own) and if they take place during the work day, or interrupt our research schedule, that is perfectly acceptable and we can readjust.

Accessibility

Whether or not you choose to disclose any needs you might have, I am committed to creating an accessible research environment. Please make me aware if some activities or tasks are inaccessible or prohibitive and we can adjust accordingly (an example, lifting heavy boxes on

our way to field work). Even if it's not documented, feel free to talk with me if we need to adjust research expectations. Virginia Tech's accessibility resources: <https://vt.edu/accessibility.html>

Learning New Skills

In our research experience together, I hope to teach you things that you do not know, how to problem solve (try turning it off and turning it on again), and to help you explore new skills that you would like to learn. For each project, we will define a set of aims, goals, and ideally what the finished task should look like.

Generally, are there specific skills you would like to learn in our lab?

Time Expectations

In the beginning, we will agree on a set number of hours and time windows where you will come in and work. This requirement is to make sure that I am present to answer any questions you may have. I do understand that an undergraduate schedule can be unpredictable; however, we will do our best to plan in time.

As our working relationship progresses, you can decide on your own working hours, as long as research goals are being met.

Working Alone, Working Hours, and Best Working Times

Normal working hours for our working relationship are defined between 8 am - 6 or 7 pm, Monday through Friday. This is an 11 hour time window because people arrive at different times and stay until different times. I often arrive between 8 and 9 am and stay until 5 or 6:30 pm. It can be variable, and that's okay.

You may notice grad students who work outside of normal (how I have defined) work hours. They may have shorter or longer days depending on their tasks for the day and whether they choose to work in a coffee shop or need to collect data. While my preference is that we all work the same hours, academia allows for flexibility. Some grad students work best 10 am - 6 pm, or 12 pm - 8 pm.

During normal lab hours 8 am - 6 pm (Mon-Fri), you are welcome to work in the lab on computer work since someone is likely around (even if not immediately present in lab). Again, in the beginning, work hours will be more "set" to make sure someone (myself) is available to answer questions. If you want to do computer work on the weekend remotely, let's discuss 1) if it's necessary and 2) hours and how long you should be doing that outside of a normal workday.

If you are performing experiments, we will discuss working alone. In the beginning, someone should be around and no experiments will be performed outside of normal lab hours without someone present.

Presentation and Public Speaking

Scientists can present their work in a myriad of ways: on Twitter through long threads and tons of gifs, through paintings/drawings/jewelry, 30 second speed talks, Science by the pint (where you present your research at a local bar/brewery), in a department seminar, on a poster (usually a printed poster of 3ft by 4ft), or even just while grocery shopping. Whether for a class or for your parents, we will also discuss effective ways to share your science, how to make slides for presentations, and how to design posters.

Lab Meeting

This is a time for the entire lab to come together and discuss any aspect of the lab. We start lab meeting with “housekeeping.” Is there cleaning that needs to be done? Do we need more paper towels? Then, we’ll get into a research topic. It’s an important time to connect, especially because faculty and grad students may have mismatched work schedules.

My expectation is that you will **present your research at lab meeting 1x per semester**. We will work together, once you are further along in your research, to prepare you for the meeting.

I also have the expectation that **you will attend 1 lab meeting per month**. If this conflicts with class or an important study group, then you do not need to attend lab meetings and we will reschedule your research presentation to the lab for a non-conflicting time.

Travel

If you are traveling for school or study abroad (extended periods, non-holidays, religious holidays), please let me know so that we can discuss a change in work expectations. For myself, if I am traveling during regular work times, I will make you aware of [my schedule through an online calendar](#) and let you know who would be best to ask questions.

Attending Conferences

As our research relationship progresses, if it becomes productive for both of us, you may want to attend an annual conference I go to, the [Society for Integrative and Comparative Biology](#). I bring students to these conferences to: present research, network with faculty, meet other scientists, and to be inspired by research across the world. Attending a national conference requires a significant amount of work and responsibility that could entail: dedicated research for a semester (5-10 hrs per week, ideally longer than a semester) or a full summer research experience (30-40 hour per week). There are also other conferences and depending on research interests and how those change, we can prepare. Note: attending a conference requires significant funding, that may not be guaranteed.

Funding

If there is a need for research funds, we will work together to find applicable grants that may be offered through the college. When attending a conference, some costs can be up front and need to be reimbursed (example: you would buy your flight and be reimbursed from the department up to a month later). Reimbursement is not ideal, but I will be honest about any potential costs and how we will deal with them together.

Volunteer versus Paid Research

A research relationship requires trust on both sides -- if we do research together, I will be present and engaged and I expect similar behavior from you. If you are paid or unpaid, expectations for working together and established hours must be respected. However, if you are a paid researcher, research tasks and number of hours will increase as that should be a primary focus. Typically undergraduate researchers in the Socha Lab are volunteers, but some exceptions occur in special circumstances.

Inclusive Science

As an undergraduate member in our lab you will be working with and around a diverse group of students, both undergraduate and graduate. In the workplace, and in our science, we strive for respect, courtesy, and understanding of others' backgrounds. Not everyone has the same science background, not everyone knows the same things. You may be completing a task that a graduate student doesn't know how to do yet. You may have knowledge that another labmate does not yet have.

In no situation should anyone ever be made to feel "less" because they don't know something. This is a learning and training environment.

Understanding Your Privilege in Science

Privilege in science can mean so many different things: you were exposed to the science process as a child, your parents are scientists, you had research experiences before college, or perhaps you learned to code in high school. Privilege is afforded through racial, social, and economic means. As an incoming researcher, it's important to reflect on personal privilege.

Science is not a place of equality, yet there are those of us that are working towards dismantling former foundations. There are many examples of inequality, but I want you to think on the right to vote. While women's (white) suffrage allowed voting in 1920 with the passage of the 19th Amendment, black women were not allowed to vote until the Voting Rights Act of 1965. Imagine how this affected how men and women of color. Imagine how structured racism affected opportunity and access to jobs.

As a scientist, it is my personal responsibility to make sure that I challenge any discrimination or racism that I encounter or see affecting others. As a white Latinx scientist, it is also my duty to recognize the privilege I have had, and to make sure that I uplift, make room, and get out of the

way of brilliant scientists of color from diverse backgrounds. As a queer/bisexual person, it is also my duty to make sure that I challenge any discrimination towards another person’s identity.

These statements and reflections are important in starting our research relationship, and if you would like to discuss these points further, we can definitely make some tea and talk.

Land Acknowledgement - [Statement from Virginia Tech](#)

“We acknowledge the Tutelo/Monocan people, who are the traditional custodians of the land on which we work and live, and recognize their continuing connection to the land, water, and air that Virginia Tech consumes. We pay respect to the Tutelo/Monocan Nations, and to their elders past, present, and emerging.”

Why do we recognize the land? Statement from Virginia Tech

“To recognize the land is an expression of gratitude and appreciation of those whose [homeland] you reside on, and a way of honoring the Indigenous people who have been living and working on the land from time immemorial. It is important to understand the long-standing history that has brought you to reside on the land, and to seek to understand your place within that history.

Land acknowledgements do not exist in a past tense, or historical context: colonialism is a current ongoing process, and we need to build our mindfulness of our present participation. It is also worth noting that acknowledging the land is Indigenous protocol.”

I acknowledge that I have read this document and agree to the expectations established between myself and Dr. Salcedo.

_____ (signature) _____ (date)

I, Dr. Salcedo acknowledge that I have read this document and agree to the expectations established between myself and _____.

_____ (signature) _____ (date)